

On the Polarographic Estimation of Gum Arabic

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In a previous publication¹, a quick and convenient polarographic method was reported for the estimation of gum arabic, which could be utilised for the routine estimation of the gum. Curves obtained for polarographs of the purified sample, taken at different concentrations with 0.1 *M*-KCl as supporting electrolyte and dextrin as a suppressor, showed only one peak with half-wave potential at -1.5 volts; the values of i_d were observed to be strictly proportional to concentration. But later on certain peculiar observations with other specimens of gum arabic forced us to repeat these experiments in the cases of gum arabic from different sources and supplied by different farms. Even the same company's gum arabic (gum acacia) was taken from a different bottle and examined by the same procedure. In all these cases, two waves closely situated with respect to each other were obtained, as shown in Fig. 1.

Three different samples were examined by the Cambridge Pen-writing polarograph.

Fig. 1

Conc. of gum arabia = 2% in aq. soln.

Starting potential = -0.6 volt.

Half-wave ,, of $E_{\frac{1}{2}}(1)$ = -1.06 ,,

Do of $E_{\frac{1}{2}}(2)$ = -1.58 ,,

The polarographic waves in each case showed two breaks in the negative potential side, *i.e.*, with the d.m.e. as the cathode. These breaks or waves were very close to each other (Fig. 1). Half-wave potential of the first wave ($E_{\frac{1}{2}}(1)$) and that of the second wave ($E_{\frac{1}{2}}(2)$) showed slight variations, changing from -1.06 to -1.08 volts and -1.54 to -1.58 volts respectively. These experiments were confirmed by several repetitions with each sample. Sometimes 25 to 30 repetitions were resorted to. In some cases the concentration of the gum was the same; in others, the concentrations were allowed to vary within the range 1, 2, 3, and 4%. Supporting electrolyte (KCl) used had always the same concentration, *viz.*, 0.1 *M* (final concentration) and

the suppressor of the concentration 0.07% dextrin. In all these cases (which, with different samples, ranged up to 100 repetitions) two waves were observed with the $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ values the same as above. The values of i_d for the two waves, when added together, bore a linear relationship with concentration, having the same value for 1% solution (*viz.* 0.83 μ a) with each of the samples. In the following tables E and i_d values are presented as $E_{\frac{1}{2}}(1)$, $E_{\frac{1}{2}}(2)$ and $i_d(1)$ and $i_d(2)$ respectively for three different varieties of gum samples.

Other gum samples behaved exactly similarly even when the concentrations of the supporting electrolyte were changed to 0.2, 0.3, 0.4 and 1 *M* respectively of KCl or when other supporting electrolytes like 0.1 *M*-NaCl, 0.1 *M*-NH₄Cl, and 0.1 *M*-NaNO₃ were used.

1. Mukherjee and Roy, *this Journal*, 1963, 40, 149.

Lastly, it was considered worthwhile to purify the gum again several times to examine whether purification of the gum might change the nature of the polarograms. For this reason purification of the gum was done by precipitating up to 7 or 8 times with ethanol. Gum samples at every step of purification were tested polarographically with gum concentration (2%) and supporting electrolyte (0.1M-KCl). All such polarograms had the same $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ and i_d values and the graphs all presented the same appearance.

TABLE I

Gum acacia samples—Stafford Allen & Sons (SAS) and Crown Drug House (CDH)

Supporting electrolyte = 0.1M-KCl. Suppressor = 0.07% dextrin.
Temperature = 30°. Drop time = 3.0 sec.

Sample No.	Conc. of gum arabic in aq. soln.	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}(1)$.	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}(2)$.	$i_d(1)$.	$i_d(2)$.	$i_d(1) + i_d(2)$.
1 (S.A.S)	2 %	-1.06 volts	-1.58 volts	0.35 μ a	1.25 μ a	1.60 μ a
2 (S.A.S)	2	-1.06	-1.56	0.30	1.20	1.50
3 (C.D.H.)	2	-1.08	-1.58	0.49	1.20	1.69

TABLE II

Gum acacia sample of Stafford Allen & Sons Ltd.

Condition same as in Table I

Conc. of gum arabic in aq. soln.	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}(1)$.	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}(2)$.	$i_d(1)$.	$i_d(2)$.	$i_d(1) + i_d(2)$.
1 %	-1.06 volts	-1.58 volts	0.23 μ a	0.60 μ a	0.83 μ a
2	-1.06	-1.58	0.35	1.25	1.60
3	-1.08	-1.54	0.53	1.65	2.18
4	-1.08	-1.54	0.76	2.28	3.03

It was next examined how other gums besides gum acacia behaved in the polarograph. For this purpose gum *Jeol*, *Guar* gum and *Neem* gum were collected from their natural sources and purified 3 to 5 times by the procedure mentioned above. Solutions (1%) of gums were tested polarographically with 0.1 M-KCl.

In the cases of gum *Jeol* and *Guar* gum, two distinct waves were observed. In the case of *Neem* gum, only one wave was visible. The $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ and i_d values obtained in these cases are recorded in Table III.

TABLE II

Condition same as in Table I

Nature.	Conc. in aq. soln.	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}(1)$.	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}(2)$.	$i_d(1)$.	$i_d(2)$.	$i_d(1) + i_d(2)$.
<i>Jeol</i>	1 %	-1.1. volts	-1.64 volts	0.23 μ a	0.68 μ a	0.90 μ a
<i>Guar</i>	1	-1.10	-1.60	0.63	1.25	1.88
<i>Neem</i>	1	-1.08	..	0.81	..	0.71

Incidentally, it may be mentioned that in course of these experiments, the instrument was repeatedly checked with a standard cadmium solution with 0.1 *M*-KCl and 0.005% gelatin, as recommended by the instrument makers. The instrument behaved uniformly all along.

From the above facts it can be concluded that gum arabic actually presents two distinct waves in general, lying very close to each other. In our previous publication¹ the single wave of gum arabic (as observed by us) might be due to the overlapping of these two closely situated waves. The appearance of two waves instead of one does not invalidate the method of estimation, as suggested therein, because the sum total of the i_d values of the two waves is within experimental accuracy nearly equal to that due to the single wave with gum arabic in the previous communication¹. In both the cases, the linear relationship between the total i_d values and the concentration of gum arabic is maintained.

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